

CZECH MALE PROPER NAMES OF LATIN ORIGIN

[Gergana PETKOVA](#)

Senior Lecturer, Ph. D.

(Medical University of Plovdiv, Bulgaria)

gi4e82ap@abv.bg

Abstract

The research object of the present text consists in Czech male proper names of Latin origin. The main aim is to present their full list, as well as to check their initial meaning.

The anthroponyms under research are divided into three major groups according to: (1) the type of the Latin name, from which the Czech one is derived; (2) their derivation, i. e. the type of the basic word, used during the process of name coining, as a part of speech; (3) the canonization of the studied names.

Keywords: Czech male proper name, Latin origin, anthroponym, meaning, derivation

Rezumat

Cercetarea este axată pe un șir de nume proprii de bărbați, înregistrate în limba cehă, care au origine latină. Scopul principal este de a le repertoria și de a cerceta semnificația lor inițială. Antroponimele date sunt clasificate în baza următoarelor principii: (1) tipul unității din latină, de la care descinde numele în cehă; (2) tipul derivației care stă la baza creării numelui în cehă; (3) canonizarea numelor în cauză.

Cuvinte-cheie: nume propriu de bărbat din cultura cehă, origine latină, antroponim, semnificație, derivare

The research object of the present text consists in 157 Czech male proper names of Latin origin. The main aim is to present their full list, as well as to check their initial meaning.

The anthroponyms under research are divided into three major groups according to: 1) the type of the Latin name, from which the Czech one is derived; 2) their derivation, i. e. the type of the basic word, used during the process of name coining, as a part of speech; 3) the canonization of the studied names.

It is very important to be underlined that the second classification is done according to the Latin grammatical rules.

The analyzed anthroponyms are excerpted from Knappová (1985), www.behindthename.com and <http://kurufin.narod.ru/>.

1. Classification of the Czech Male Proper Names of Latin Origin According to the Basic Latin Name

We distinguish:

- Czech male proper names of Latin origin, derived from a Roman mythological name: *Honor* (< Honor/Honos), *Libor* (< Leber/Liber), *Remus* (< Remus), *Romus* (< Romulus), *Saturn* (< Saturnus), *Silvân* (< Silvanus);

- Czech male proper names of Latin origin, derived from a Roman praenomen: *Cézar* (< Caesar), *Gajus/Kájus* (< Caius/Cajus/Gaius), *Faust* (< Faustus), *Lucius* (< Lucius), *Marek* (< Marcus), *Oktavius* (< Octavius), *Pavel* (< Paullus/Paulus), *Sixt* (< Sextus/Sixstus), *Tiber* (< Tiberius), *Titus* (< Titus);
- Czech male proper names of Latin origin, derived from a Roman gentile name: *Anton* (< Antonius), *Antonín* (< Antoninus), *August* (< Augustus), *Augustýn* (< Augustinus), *Aurel* (< Aurelius), *Cecil* (< Caecilius), *Cyprián* (< Cyprianus), *Emil* (< Aemilius), *Fabius* (< Fabius), *Flavián* (< Flavianus), *Flavius* (< Flavius), *Havel* (< Gallus), *Horác* (< Horatius/Oratius), *Ignác* (< Egnatius/Ignatius), *Julius* (< Iuleus/Iulius/Julius), *Kasián* (< Cassian/Cassianus), *Klaudián* (< Claudianus), *Klaudius* (< Claudius/Clodius), *Kornel* (< Cornelius), *Livius* (< Livius), *Lucián* (< Lucianus), *Lukrécius* (< Lucretius), *Marcel* (< Marcellus), *Marcelín* (< Marcellinus), *Marcianus* (< Marcianus), *Marián* (< Marianus), *Marin* (< Marinus), *Marius* (< Marius), *Oktavius* (< Octavius), *Ovidius* (< Ovidius), *Petronius* (< Petronius), *Sergej* (< Sergius), *Sever* (< Severus), *Severin* (< Severinus), *Terenc* (< Terentius), *Vergilius/Virgilius* (< Vergilius/Virgilius), *Virgin* (< Verginius/Virginus);
- Czech male proper names of Latin origin, derived from a Roman cognomen: *Adrián/Hadrián* (< Adrianus/Hadrianus), *Alban* (< Albanus), *Albín* (< Albinus), *Aurelián* (< Aurelianus), *Cézar* (< Caesar), *Donát* (< Donatus), *Fabián* (< Fabianus), *Faustýn* (< Faustinus), *Faust* (< Faustus), *Felicián* (< Felicianus), *Felix* (< Felix), *Florentius* (< Florentius), *Florián* (< Florianus), *Havel* (< Gallus), *Januarius* (< Ianuarius/Januarius), *Julián* (< Iulianus/Julianus), *Justýn* (< Iustinus/Justinus), *Kamil* (< Camillus), *Kryšpín* (< Crispinus), *Laurenc* (< Laurentius), *Laurentýn* (< Laurentinus), *Mauricius* (< Mauricius/Mauritius), *Maxim* (< Maximus), *Oktavián* (< Octavianus), *Pavel* (< Paullus/Paulus), *Pavln* (< Paulinus/Paullinus), *Rufinus* (< Rufinus), *Rufus* (< Rufus), *Saturnin* (< Saturninus), *Sever* (< Severus), *Sixt* (< Sextus/Sixstus), *Tibor* (< Tiburtius), *Torkoát* (< Torquatus), *Urban* (< Urbanus), *Valentýn* (< Valentinus), *Valerián* (< Valerianus), *Viktor* (< Victor), *Viktorián* (< Victorianus), *Viktorin* (< Victorinus), *Vincenc* (< Vincentius);
- Czech male proper names of Latin origin, derived from a Roman agnomen: *Felix* (< Felix), *Silvius* (< Silvius);
- Czech male proper names of Latin origin, derived from a Neolatin name: *Amadeus* (< Amadeus), *Amand* (< Amandus), *Amát* (< Amatus), *Beatus* (< Beatus), *Benedikt* (< Benedictus), *Blažej* (< Blasius), *Bonaventura* (< Bonaventura), *Bonifác* (< Bonifatius/Bonifacius/Bonifatius), *Brit* (< Britannus), *Celestýn* (< Caelestinus/Coelestinus), *Dezider* (< Desiderius), *Dominik* (< Dominicus), *Eligijs* (< Eligius), *Fidel* (< Fidelis), *Florentýn* (< Florentinus), *Fortunát* (< Fortunatus), *František* (< Franciscus), *Gabin* (<

Gabinus), *Gracián* (< Gratianus), *Grant* (< Grantus), *Haštal* (< Castulus), *Hilar* (< Hilarius), *Honorius* (< Honorius), *Inocenc* (< Innocentius), *Kajetán* (< Caietanus/Gaetanus), *Klement* (< Clemens), *Kolumbán* (< Columbanus), *Kolombín* (< Columbinus), *Konstantýn* (< Constantinus), *Krescenc* (< Crescens), *Kristián* (< Christianus), *Leo* (< Leo), *Libor* (< Liberalis), *Lukáš* (< Lucas), *Magnus* (< Magnus), *Martin* (< Martinus), *Maximilián* (< Maximilianus), *Moric* (< Maurus), *Modest* (< Modestus), *Oliver* (< Oliver), *Paskal* (< Paschalis), *Patrik* (< Patricius/Patritius), *Pelhřim* (< Peregrinus), *Pius* (< Pius), *Placidus* (< Placidus), *Prosper* (< Prosper/Prosperus), *Reginald* (< Reginaldus), *Remig* (< Remigius), *Renát* (< Renatus), *Roman* (< Romanus), *Sebastian* (< Sebastianus), *Serenus* (< Serenus), *Servoác* (< Servatius), *Sidon* (< Sidonius), *Silver* (< Silverius), *Silvestr* (< Silvester), *Vincenc* (< Vicentius), *Vít* (< Vitus), *Vivian* (< Bibianus/Vivianus).

2. Classification of the Czech Male Proper Names of Latin Origin According to the Basic Derivational Word as a Part of Speech

We distinguish:

- (a) Czech male proper names of Latin origin, derived from:
- a Roman mythological name: *Martin* (< Martinus < Martis, Gen. sg. of Mars), *Saturnin* (< Saturninus < Saturnus);
 - a Roman praenomen: *Lucián* (< Lucianus < Lucius), *Oktavián* (< Octavianus < Octavius), *Pavlín* (< Paulinus/Paullinus < Paulus);
 - a Roman gentile name: *Antonín* (< Antoninus < Antonius), *Augustýn* (< Augustinus < Augustus), *Aurelián* (< Aurelianus < Aurelius), *Emilián* (< Aemilianus < Aemilius), *Fabián* (< Fabianus < Fabius), *Flavián* (< Flavianus < Flavius), *Julián* (< Iulianus/Julianus < Iuleus/Iulius/ Julius), *Kasián* (< Cassian/Cassianus < Cassius), *Klaudián* (< Claudianus < Claudius), *Marcianus* (< Marcianus < Marcius), *Severin* (< Severinus < Severus), *Valerián* (< Valerianus < Valerius);
 - a Roman cognomen: *Faustýn* (< Faustinus < Faustus), *Felicián* (< Felicianus < Felix), *Rufinus* (< Rufinus < Rufus), *Viktorián* (< Victorianus < Victor);
 - a Neolatin name: *Kolumbán* (< Columbanus < Columba), *Kolombín* (< Columbinus < Columba);
- (b) Czech male proper names of Latin origin, derived from an appellative, which is:
- a common noun: *Brit* (< Britannus < Britannus, *-i*, m - "British"), *Fabius* (< Fabius < faba, *-ae*, f - "bean"), *František* (< Franciscus < Franciscus, *-i*, m - "French"), *Honor* (< Honor/Honos < honor, *-oris*, m - "honour"), *Horác* (< Horatius/Oratius < hora, *-ae*, f - "hour, time, season"), *Leo* (< Leo < leo, *-onis*, m - "lion"), *Pelhřim* (<

Peregrinus < peregrinus, -i, m - "pilgrim"), *Ovidius* (< Ovidius < -ovis, -is, f - "sheep"), *Reginald* (< Reginaldus < regina, -ae, f - "queen"), *Silvan* (< Silvanus < silva, -ae, f - "forest"), *Viktor* (< Victor < victor, -oris, m - "winner");

- an adjective: *Celestyn* (< Caelestinus/Coelestinus < caelestinus, 3/caelestis, e/coelestis, e - "celestial"), *Cyprian* (< Cyprianus < Cyprianus, 3 - "from Cyprus"), *Faust* (< Faustus < faustus, 3 - "lucky; happy"), *Felix* (< Felix < felix, icis - "happy; lucky; successful"), *Fidel* (< Fidelis < fidelis, e - "faithful"), *Fortunat* (< Fortunatus < fortunatus, 3 - "happy; lucky"), *Gabin* (< Gabinus < Gabinus, 3 - "from Gabius"), *Grant* (< Grantus < grandis, e - "great"), *Hilar* (< Hilarius < hilaris, e/hilarus, 3 - "happy"), *Inocenc* (< Innocentius < innocens, entis - "innocent"), *Januarius* (< Ianuarius/ Januarius < Ianuarius, 3 - "belonging to Janus"), *Kajetan* (< Caietanus/ Gaetanus < Caietanus, 3/Caetanus, 3 - "from Caiete"), *Klement* (< Clemens < clemens, entis - "kind"), *Konstantyn* (< Constantinus < constans, antis - "constant"), *Libor* (< Leber/Liber < liber, era, erum - "free; independent"), *Magnus* (< Magnus < magnus, 3 - "big; great"), *Maxim* (< Maximus < maximus, 3 - "the greatest"), *Modest* (< Modestus < modestus, 3 - "modest"), *Moric* (< Maurus < maurus, 3 - "dark-skinned"), *Oktavius* (< Octavius < octavus, 3 - "eighth"), *Oliver* (< Oliver < olivifer, fera, ferum - "giving olive oil"), *Pavel* (< Paullus/Paulus < paullus, 3/paulus, 3 - "small; modest"), *Pius* (< Pius < pius, 3 - "pious"), *Placidus* (< Placidus < placidus, 3 - "quiet; paeceful"), *Prosper* (< Prosper/Prosperus < prosperus, 3 - "prosperous"), *Romul* (< Romulus < Romulus, 3 - "Roman"), *Rufus* (< Rufus < rufus, 3 - "redhead"), *Sebastian* (< Sebastianus < Sebastianus, 3 - "Sebastian"), *Serenus* (< Serenus < serenus, 3 - "calm"), *Sever* (< Severus < severus, 3 - "serious; stict"), *Sidon* (< Sidonius < Sidonius, 3 - "from Sidon"), *Sixt* (< Sextus/Sixstus < sextus, 3 - "sixth") , *Tiber* (< Tiberius < Tiberius, 3 - "belonging to the Tiber River"), *Tibor* (< Tiburtius < лат. Tiburtius, 3 - "belonging to Tibur"), *Torkvat* (< Torquatus < torquatus, 3 - "with a necklace (martial honour)"), *Urban* (< Urbanus < urbanus, 3 - "urban");
- a verboid: *Amand* (< Amandus < amandus, 3 - "beloved" (gerundius of the verb amo, 1 - "to love"), *Amat* (< Amatus < amatus, 3 - "loved" (past participle of the verb amo, 1 - "to love"), *August* (< Augustus < augustus, 3 - "great" (past participle of the verb augeo, 2 - "to enlarge"), *Donat* (< Donatus < donatus, 3 - "given, presented" (past participle of the verb dono, 1 - "to give, to present")), *Florentius* (< Florentius < florens, entis - "flourishing" (present participle of the verb floreo, 2 - "to flower")), *Krescenc* (<

Crescens < crescens, entis - "growing" (present participle of the verb cresco, 3 - "to grow"), *Renát* (< Renatus < renatus, 3 - "reborn" (past participle of the verb renascor, 3 - "to be born again");

(c) Czech male proper names of Latin origin, derived from:

- an objective syntagma: *Amadeus* (< Amadeus < amo, 1 - "to love" and Deus, -i, m - "God");

- an attributive syntagma: *Bonaventura* (< Bonaventura < bona - "good" (feminine form of the adjective bonus, 3 - "good") and ventura, -ae, f - "chance, fate");

(d) Czech male personal names of Latin origin with uncertain etymology:

Alban (< Albanus < 1) Albanus, 3 - "from Alba"; 2) albus, 3 - "white"), *Albín* (< Albinus < 1) a Roman cognomen Albus; 2) albinus, 3 - "the white one"), *Anton* (< Antonius < 1) Antenium, an Etruscan name of unclear origin; 2) Greek ανθος - "flower"; 3) Greek αντέω < αντιάω - "to take part in a fight"), *Aurel* (< Aurelius < 1) aureolus, 3/ aureus, 3 - "golden"; 2) aurum, i, n - "gold"), *Beatus* (< Beatus < 1) female name Beata; 2) beatus, 3 - "blessed; happy"), *Benedikt* (< Benedictus < benedictus, 3 - "laudable" (past participle of the verb benedico, 3 - "to praise someone"); 2) benedico, 3 - "to praise someone"), *Blažej* (< Blasius < 1) blaesus, 3 - "fleece"; 2) blatio, 4 - "to blab"; 3) Greek βλάσιος - "bowlegged"), *Bonifác* (< Bonifatius/Bonifacius/Bonifatius < 1) homo boni fati - "good fortune; a person with good deeds"; 2) bonum - "good" (neutral form of the adjective bonus, 3 - "good") and fatum - "fate"; 3) bonus, 3 - "good" and faciens, entis - "doing" (present participle of the verb facio, 3 - "to do")), *Cecil* (< Caecilius < 1) caecus, 3 - "blind"; 2) cado, 3 - "to fall"), *Cézar* (< Caesar < 1) caesaries, ei, f - "hair"; 2) caedo, 3 - "to cut"), *Dezider* (< Desiderius < 1) desiderium, ii, n - "longing, desire"; 2) desiderius, 3 - "desired"; 3) desidero, 1 - "to desire, to long"), *Dominik* (< Dominicus < dominicus, 3 - "belonging to the master/God"; 2) dies Dominicus - "God's day; Sunday" < dies, diei, m/f - "day" and Dominicus, 3 - "belonging to God"), *Eligius* (< Eligius < 1) eligo, 3 - "to select"; 2) eligius, 3 - "selected" (past participle of the verb eligo, 3 - "to select"), *Emil* (< Aemilius < 1) aemulus, -i, m - "enemy"; 2) aemilius, 3 - "hostile"; 3) Greek αμβλιος - "glittering"), *Flavius* (< Flavius < 1) flavus, 3 - "yellow; blond"; 2) Flavius, -ii, m - "Flavian"), *Florentýn* (< Florentinus < 1) florens, -entis - "flourishing" (present participle of the verb floreo, 2 - "to flower"); 2) Florentinus, 3/Florentinus, -i, m - "Florentian"), *Florián* (< Florianus < 1) a Roman cognomen Florus; 2) florianus, 3 - "flourishing"), *Gajus/ Kájus* (< Caius/Cajus/Gaius (< 1) unclear meaning; 2) gaudeo, 2 - "to enjoy"), *Gracián* (< Gratianus < 1) gratus,

3 - "kind; grateful"; 2) gratianus, 3 - "grateful"; 3) gratia, ae, f - "grace; kindness"), *Haštal* (< Castulus < 1) castus, 3 - "innocent"; 2) castellum, i, n - "castle"; 3) castulus, 3 - "innocent (diminutive form)", *Havel* (< Gallus < 1) gallus, i, m - "rooster"; 2) Gallus, i, m - "Gaul"), *Honorius* (< Honorius < 1) honorius, 3 - "honest"; 2) honoro, 1 - "honorable"), *Ignác* (< Egnatius/Ignatius < 1) unclear meaning; 2) ignis, is, m - "fire"; 3) gnatus, 3 - "born" (past participle of the verb gnascor, 3 - "to be born"); 4) ignotus, 3 - "unknown"; 5) igneus, 3 - "fiery"), *Julius* (< Iuleus/Iulius/Julius < 1) Greek ιουλος - "curly"; 2) Iovilius, 3 - "belonging to Jupiter"), *Justýn* (< Iustinus/Justinus < 1) iustus, 3 - "fair"; 2) male name Iustus), *Kamil* (< Camillus < 1) unclear meaning; 2) camillus, i, m - "young religious servant"), *Klaudius* (< Claudius/Clodius < 1) claudus, 3 - "lame"; 2) claudeo, 2 - "to become lame"; 3) claudius, 3 - "locked"), *Kornel* (< Cornelius < 1) cornu, us, n - "horn"; 2) corneus, 3 - "insensitive"; 3) corneolus, 3 - "hard"; 4) cornum, i, n - "strawberry"), *Kristián* (< Christianus < christianus, i, m/christianus, 3 - "a Christian/Christian"), *Kryšpín* (< Crispinus < 1) a Roman cognomen Crispus; 2) crispinus, 3 - "curly"), *Laurenc* (< Laurentius < 1) Laurentius, 3 - "from Laurentius"; 2) laurentius, 3 - "crowned with a laurel wreath"), *Laurentýn* (< Laurentinus < 1) a Roman cognomen Laurentius; 2) Laurentinus, 3 - "Lavrentian"), *Livius* (< Livius < 1) liveo, 2 - "to be envy; to become blue"; 2) livor, oris, m - "envy"; 3) lividus, 3 - "envious"), *Lucius* (< Lucius < 1) lux, lucis, f - "light"; 2) loucus, 3 - "bright"), *Lukáš* (< Lucas < 1) Greek Λουκάς - "from Lucania"; 2) lucus, i, m - "forest, dedicated to the gods"; 3) lux, lucis, f - "light"), *Lukrécius* (< Lucretius < 1) lucrum, i, n - "richness"; 2) lucretius, 3 - "to benefit"), *Marcel* (< Marcellus < 1) a diminutive form of the Roman praenomen Marcus; 2) marcellus, i, m - "little hammer"), *Marcelín* (< Marcellinus < 1) a Roman gentile name Marcellus; 2) marcellus, i, m - "little hammer"), *Marek* (< Marcus < 1) Roman mythological name Mars; 2) mas, maris - "male"; 3) marcus, i, m - "hammer"; 4) marceo, 2 - "to be exhausted"), *Marián* (< Marianus < 1) a Roman gentile name Marius; 2) a female Biblical name Maria), *Marin* (< Marinus < 1) a Roman gentile name Marius; 2) marinus, 3 - "marine"; 3) mare, -is, n - "sea"; 4) a Roman mythological name Mars (44); 5) a female Biblical name Maria (rare from the female name Marina)), *Marius* (< Marius < 1) a Roman mythological name Mars; 2) mas, maris - "male"; 3) mare, is, n - "sea"), *Mauricius* (< Mauricius/Mauritius < 1) male name Maurus; 2) mauricius, 3 - "Maverick"; 3) Mauritius, 3 - "from Mauritania"), *Maximilián* (< Maximilianus < 1) a Roman cognomen Maximus; 2) combination between the anthroponyms

Maximus and Aemilianus), *Paskal* (< Paschalis < 1) Paschalis, e - "linked with the Easter"; 2) Pascha, ae, f - "Easter"); *Patrik* (< Patricius/ Patritius < 1) patricius, ii, m - "patrician"; 2) patritus, 3 - "paternal"), *Petronius* (< Petronius < 1) petro, petronis, m - "foozle; old ram"; 2) Greek πέτρα/πέτρος - "stone; rock"), *Remig* (< Remigius < 1) remex, remigis, m - "rower"; 2) remigium, ii, n - "row"), *Remus* (< Remus < 1) unclear meaning; 2) remus, i, m - "row"), *Roman* (< Romanus < 1) Romanus, i, m/ Romanus, 3 - "a Roman/Roman"), *Saturn* (< Saturnus < 1) unclear meaning; 2) satur, ura, urum - "fruitful"; 3) sero, 1 - "to seed"; 4) sator, oris, m - "seedsman"), *Sergej* (< Sergius < 1) servus, i, m - "slave"; 2) Greek σέργιος - "guard"; 3) unclear meaning), *Servoác* (< Servatius < 1) servatus, 3 - "saved, kept" (past participle from the verb servo, 1 - "to keep"); 2) servo, 1 - "to keep"; 3) servator, oris, m - "savior"), *Silver* (< Silverius < 1) nickname of the Alba Longa legendary kings; 2) silva, ae, f - "forest"; 3) silverius, 3 - "silvan"), *Silvestr* (< Silvester < 1) silva, ae, f - "forest"; 2) silvester, tra, trum/ silvestris, e - "silvan"), *Silvoius* (< Silvius < 1) silva, ae, f - "forest"; 2) silvius, 3 - "silvan"), *Terenc* (< Terentius < 1) unclear meaning; 2) terens, entis - "friction" (present participle from the verb tero, 3 - "to rub"); 3) terentius, 3 - "deleted"; 4) teres, teretis - "slim"), *Titus* (< Titus < 1) unclear meaning; 2) titulus, i, m - "title"; 3) tueor, tuitus, tutus sum, 2 - "to watch"; 4) an Etruscan word titus - "to defend"), *Valentýn* (< Valentinus < 1) valens, entis - "healthy" (present participle from the verb valeo, 2 - "to be healthy"); 2) valentia, ae, f - "power"; 3) valentinus, 3 - "a healthy person"), *Vergilius/Virgilius* (< Vergilius/Virgilius < 1) virens, entis - "greenish" (present participle from the verb vireo, 2 - "to become green"); 2) virgo, inis, f - "virgin"; 3) virgula, ae, f - "twig"; 4) virga, ae, f - "rod"; 5) vergiliae, arum, f - "Constellation Pleiades"; 6) vireo, 2 - "to be greenish"), *Viktorin* (< Victorinus < 1) a Roman cognomen Victor; 2) victorinus, 3 - "winning"), *Vincenc* (< Vincentius < 1) vinco, 3 - "to win"; 2) vincens, entis - "winning" (present participle from the verb vinco, 3 - "to win")), *Virgin* (< Verginius/Virginus < 1) virgo, inis, f - "virgin"; 2) virginus, 3 - "virgin"; 3) virga, ae, f - "rod"; 4) vergo, 3 - "to be declined"), *Vivian* (< Bibianus/Vivianus < 1) vivus, 3 - "alive"; 2) vivo, 3 - "to live"), *Vít* (< Vitus < 1) vita, ae, f - "life"; 2) vitulus, i, m - "youngster"; 3) avitus, i, m - "grand-father"; 4) vitus, 3 - "invited; wanted"; 5) vitis, is, f - "centurion"; 6) via, ae, f - "way").

3. Classification of the Czech Male Proper Names of Latin Origin According to their Canonization

We distinguish:

- names of saints, canonized by the Orthodox Church: *Grantus, Lucretius, Ovidius* etc.;
- names of saints, canonized by the Catholic Church: *Albanus, Amatus, Beatus, Bonaventura, Caecilius, Columbanus, Columbinus, Crispinus, Dominicus, Eligius, Gallus, Laurentinus, Oliver, Paschalis, Peregrinus, Reginaldus, Romulus, Servatius, Sextus/Sixstus, Sidonius, Vergilius/Virgilius,Victorianus* etc.;
- names of saints, canonized by both the Orthodox and the Catholic Churches: *Adrianus/Hadrianus, Aemilius, Albinus, Amadeus, Amandus, Antoninus, Antonius, Augustinus, Augustus, Aurelianus, Aurelius, Benedictus, Bibianus/Vivianus, Blasius, Bonifatius/Bonifacius/Bonifatius, Britannus, Caelestinus/Coelestinus, Caesar, Caietanus/Gaetanus, Caius/Cajus/Gaius, Camillus, Cassian/Cassianus, Castulus, Christianus, Claudianus, Claudius/Clodius, Clemens, Cornelius, Crescens, Cyprianus, Desiderius, Donatus, Egnatius/Ignatius, Fabianus, Fabius, Faustinus, Faustus, Felix, Fidelis, Flavianus, Flavius, Florentinus, Florianus, Fortunatus, Franciscus, Gabinus, Gallus, Gratianus, Hilarius, Honor/Honos, Honorius, Horatius/Oratius, Ianuarius/Januarius, Innocentius, Iuleus/Iulius/Julius, Iulianus/Julianus, Iustinus/Justinus, Laurentius, Leo, Liberalis, Livius, Lucas, Lucianus, Lucius, Magnus, Marcellinus, Marcellus, Marcianus, Marcus, Marianus, Marinus, Marius, Martinus, Mauricius/Mauritius, Maurus, Maximilianus, Maximus, Modestus, Octavianus, Octavius, Patricius/Patritius, Paulinus/Paullinus, Paullus/Paulus, Petronius, Pius, Placidus, Remigius, Renatus, Romanus, Rufinus, Rufus, Saturninus, Saturnus, Sebastianus, Serenus, Sergius, Severinus, Severus, Silvanus, Silverius, Silvester, Silvius, Terentius, Tiberius, Tiburtius, Titus, Torquatus, Urbanus, Valentinus, Valerianus, Victor, Victorinus, Vincentius, Vitus.*

In the classification according to the basic Latin name six subgroups are formed – Czech male proper name, derived from: 1) a Roman mythological name; 2) a Roman praenomen; 3) a Roman gentile name; 4) a Roman cognomen; 5) a Roman agnomen; 6) a Neolatin name. The biggest group is that of Czech male anthroponyms, derived from a Neolatin name, while the smallest group includes those of them, derived from a Roman agnomen.

In the second classification, according to the type of the basic Latin word, from which the Latin name, and respectively the Slavonic one, is coined, are divided into four groups: 1) from another name; 2) from an appellative; 3) from a syntagma; 4) with uncertain etymology. The biggest group is the last one.

The classification according to canonization includes: 1) names of Orthodox saints (the smallest group); 2) names of Catholic saints; 3) names of saints, canonized by both Churches (the biggest of the three groups).

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